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ECOSYSTEM MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE

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Abstract

Ecosystems sustain the climate through balancing carbon, water and other biogeochemical cycles. Greenhouse gas emission, ocean acidification, changed rainfall pattern, risk of fire and storm, deforestation causes climate change and threatens the viability and resilience of natural ecosystems and human societies. Climate change triggers a cascade of impacts in the entire ecosystem which includes species expansion into new area, intermingling of formerly non overlapping species and even species extinctions. Species decline affect the services from nature, which includes functioning as carbon sink and increasing our resilience to climate change. The endemic plants and animals face a greater threat from climate change than non-endemic and introduced species. Coffee, cocoa, avocados and wild relatives of popular crops are going extinct due to climate change. In aquatic organisms, increased water temperatures may lead to increased metabolic demand for oxygen while reducing the oxygen content of the water. The decreasing precipitation may lead to water stress, death and local extinction of terrestrial species. Coral bleaching is driven by extreme heatwaves rather than gradual ocean warming. Changes in natural ecosystems causes deflections in global food production and indirectly effect human health. Hence, it is high time that the ecosystem balance should be conserved. The ecosystem management includes maintaining wetlands and urban green spaces, increasing coastal afforestation, water shed and reservoir management and reduction of other stresses on ecosystems and of habitat fragmentation. It is extremely challenging to predict the patterns and probabilities of biodiversity loss, both from the subtle effects on individual species within complex multi-trophic ecosystems and the more abrupt effects of ecosystem degradation. So, understanding the proximate factors that cause climate-related extinctions should be an urgent priority. Periodic assessments of current and future climate change impacts on ecosystems are important for developing and updating natural resource management plans and evaluating adaptation actions.

Key words: *Climate change, biodiversity, ecosystems, ecosystem management*